

ISic1288

I.Sicily inscription 1288

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 259 + 280 + 305

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]ιος Φιλο[---]
2. ζ · ας καὶ Αὐρη
3. λια Κλωδία ἡ
4. σύνβιος μου ἐ
5. κτησάμεθα χώραν
6. καθαρὰν καὶ ἐθεμε[λιώ]
7. σαμεν καὶ ἐποιήσα[μεν]
8. κοιτῶνα ἑαυτοῦ[ςκαὶ]
9. [τοῦ]ς κληρονόμοι[ςκαὶ]
10. [εἰ]σανγέλλομεν[---]
11. [---][φθάση] ἐνθάδε[---]
12. [---]ε ον[---]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

[unnamed man] and my partner Aurelia Klodia, we acquired spotless land, firmly laid the foundation and made a grave for ourselves and for our heirs, and we declare that...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492893

EDCS 39101657

PHI 140778

PHI 316234

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0464 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 118

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